

Solvation of Cobalt(III) Complexes : Partial Molar Volumes and Transfer Chemical Potentials

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Partial molar volumes for cobalt(III) complexes in aqueous solution are reviewed, and transfer chemical potentials for this family of complexes to aqueous methanol collated. The relevance of such information to the understanding of hydration of these complexes is outlined. Preliminary results on binuclear cobalt(III) complexes are presented and discussed in relation to available data on mononuclear cobalt(III) species.

Cobalt(III) complexes have played a central role in coordination chemistry since the pioneering and extensive work of Werner and Jorgensen¹. They have also played a major part in the development of inorganic solution kinetics, both with respect to mechanisms of ligand substitution² and of electron transfer^{2,3}. In recent decades the role of the solvent in determining reactivity has increasingly come under scrutiny⁴. Despite extensive studies of kinetics of solvolysis of cobalt(III) complexes in binary aqueous mixtures^{4,5}, and considerably more limited studies of their reduction in such media^{6,7}, the amount of quantitative information on hydration and solvation of cobalt(III) complexes is rather limited. There is a large body of information on solubilities of salts of such complex cations and anions, much of it dating from half a century ago⁸. However as solubilities depend on counterion solvation and lattice energy as well as on solvation of the complex ion in question⁹, such results do not give direct information on complex ion solvation. Indeed as the accurate calculations of lattice energies needed to derive ionic solvation energies are impossible for multiatomic ions¹⁰, it is unwise to expect much progress in this direction. An alternative approach to assessing hydration is the determination of partial molar volumes. This can be achieved with considerable precision now-a-days, as long as the salt under examination is not too sparingly soluble. Results can be extrapolated with confidence to infinite dilution, and the single ion splitting assumption needed to deduce values for charged complexes does not introduce significant uncertainties. Partial molar volumes can be compared with estimates of intrinsic volumes to obtain an idea of the extent of hydration. A different approach to the assessment of solvation is to establish chemical potential trends in binary aqueous solvents. In a sense this is a more indirect approach, giving information on solvation changes rather than on solvation (hydration) directly¹¹. This approach works well if one can measure solubilities of sparingly soluble salts of inert complexes

(cobalt(III) is very satisfactory in this respect, of course) whose state of hydration in the solid phase in equilibrium with saturated solution is not affected by change of solvent medium. Again it is necessary to split whole salt values into ionic components, but this can be done with reasonable confidence¹². In this paper we deal with the two latter approaches, presenting summaries of partial molar volumes for cobalt(III) complexes in aqueous solution and of transfer chemical potentials for such complexes in methanol-water media. The main purpose of this paper is to collect together and compare such data from a variety of sources, but we also report some new results obtained in our laboratories, in particular for a small selection of binuclear complexes.

Results and Discussion

Partial molar volumes: These are available for a few dozen cobalt(III) complexes, having been determined in some cases out of intrinsic interest, in others in connection with the establishment of reaction profiles associated with the determination of activation volumes for substitution or electron transfer reactions of such complexes¹³. We have measured densities of solutions of the binuclear complex $[(\text{H}_2\text{N})_4\text{Co}(\mu\text{-NH}_2)(\mu\text{-OH})\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_4]\text{Cl}_4 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Table 1), and, from a Redlich-Mayer plot, derived a partial molar volume of $+262 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$

TABLE 1—DENSITIES OF AQUEOUS SOLUTIONS OF $[(\text{H}_2\text{N})_4\text{Co}(\mu\text{-NH}_2)(\mu\text{-OH})\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_4]\text{Cl}_4 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$, AT 298.15 K (DENSITY OF WATER = 0.997 049 g cm^{-3} AT THIS TEMPERATURE)

10^3 [complex salt] mol dm^{-3}	Density g cm^{-3}
5.43	0.998 319
7.17	0.998 712
8.19	0.998 944
9.41	0.999 214
11.88	0.999 777
12.68	0.999 959

for this salt. Then, with the aid of the published value¹⁴ of $\bar{V}(\text{Cl}^-) = +17.8$ and $\bar{V}(\text{H}_2\text{O}) = +18.0 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$, we obtain a partial molar volume of $+119 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ for this binuclear cation.

A comprehensive listing of partial molar volumes for cobalt(III) complexes in aqueous solution is available elsewhere¹⁵, so here we shall present a selection of examples and trends which illustrate how these quantities reflect solvation. In all cases we quote values relative to a value of zero for the proton. As this is almost certainly within about $\pm 5 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ of the absolute value, differences between reported and absolute values of partial molar volumes for ions are only a few percent. The situation is much more satisfactory than, for example, for transfer chemical potentials. Of course for a series of ions of constant charge, the single ion assumption used has no effect on comparisons.

The first point to make is that the effect of hydration on partial molar volumes of complex ions is large. Thus, for example, the intrinsic volume of the $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6]^{3+}$ cation is $+129 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ (Ref. 16), whereas its partial molar volume in aqueous solution is $+71 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$. Depending on the single ion assumption used, this indicates a volume decrease of between about 55 and $85 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$, attributable primarily to solvent electrostriction in the hydration shell of this ion. In general one may write,

$$\bar{V}(\text{observed}) = \bar{V}(\text{intrinsic}) + \bar{V}(\text{hydration})$$

with the latter term probably incorporating solute-solvent hydrogen-bonding as well as simple electrostriction.

The contribution of $\bar{V}(\text{intrinsic})$ can be gauged from the series of hexaammine complexes given in Table 2^{15,17-20}. This Table also shows ligand volume effects (right-hand column), though here intrinsic effects may well be slightly modified by slightly differing solute-solvent interactions, as the hydrophobicity increases the bulk increases. The combined contributions of intrinsic volume

TABLE 2—PARTIAL MOLAR VOLUMES ($\bar{V}/\text{cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$) FOR HEXA-AMMINE-METAL(III) AND BIDENTATE AMINE-COBALT(III) COMPLEXES, IN AQUEOUS SOLUTION AT 298.2 K, ASSUMING $\bar{V}(\text{H}^+) = 0$

$[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6]^{3+}$	71 ^a	$[\text{Co}(\text{en})_3]^{3+}$	130 ^d
$[\text{Rh}(\text{NH}_3)_6]^{3+}$	79 ^b	$[\text{Co}(\text{tn})_3]^{3+}$	162 ^e
$[\text{Ir}(\text{NH}_3)_6]^{3+}$	86 ^b	$[\text{Co}(\text{pn})_3]^{3+}$	223 ^d
		$[\text{Co}(\text{phen})_3]^{3+}$	384 ^e

^aRef. 15. ^bRef. 17. ^cRef. 18. ^dRef. 19. ^eRef. 20.

and hydrogen-bonding contributions can be seen in the series given in Table 3^{15,21,22}, for

**In the case of this complex and of $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5(\text{OH})]^{2+}$, $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5(\text{OH})]^{2+}$ and $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{Cl}]^{2+}$, we have used values which are means of several independent determinations, converted to be compatible with $\bar{V}(\text{H}^+) = 0$ where necessary. Full details will be found in Ref. 15.

TABLE 3—PARTIAL MOLAR VOLUMES ($\bar{V}/\text{cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$) FOR PENTA-AMMINE-COBALT(III) COMPLEXES*, IN AQUEOUS SOLUTION AT 298.2 K, ASSUMING $\bar{V}(\text{H}^+) = 0$

$[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{X}]^{2+}$		$[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{L}]^{2+}$	
X=OH	81	L=OH ₂	73
NO ₂	83	MeOH	92
Cl	85 ^a	EtOH	109
Br	95	iPrOH	125
I	95	DMSO	125
NCS	105	F ^b	95
		NMF	112
		DMF	129

*Ref. 15, 21, 22. ^aApproximate value, due to range of published estimates. ^bF=formamide

$[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5(\text{solvent})]^{2+}$ and $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{X}]^{2+}$, where X is a singly charged anionic ligand. To assess electrostatic contributions one needs a series of complexes with an identical ligand set, such as the series of tris-ethane-1,2-diamine complexes given in Table 4 (left-hand column)^{23,24}. The significance

TABLE 4—PARTIAL MOLAR VOLUMES ($\bar{V}/\text{cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$) FOR TRIS-ETHANE-1,2-DIAMINE COMPLEXES* AND FOR THE COBALT(III)-NITROAMMINE SERIES** IN AQUEOUS SOLUTION AT 298.2 K ASSUMING $\bar{V}(\text{H}^+) = 0$

$[\text{Ni}(\text{en})_3]^{2+}$	171	$[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6]^{3+}$	71
$[\text{Cr}(\text{en})_3]^{3+}$	140	$[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5(\text{NO}_2)]^{2+}$	83
$[\text{Co}(\text{en})_3]^{2+}$	130	$[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_4(\text{NO}_2)_2]^{+}$	104 ^a
$[\text{Pt}(\text{en})_3]^{4+}$	113	$[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_3(\text{NO}_2)_3]^{-}$	116
		$[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{NO}_2)_4]^{-}$	130

*Refs. 23, 24. **Ref. 25. ^atrans-Isomer.

of the electrostatic contribution is clear; the effect of the different ionic radii of the central metal cations, an inescapable variable, is minor (*cf.* above). However, the balance of electrostatic and other factors is not always straightforward, as is shown by the series of cobalt(III)-nitroammine complexes (Table 4, right-hand column)²⁵ and Fig. 1. Here there is no discontinuity or extremum at the uncharged complex;

Fig. 1. Correlation of partial molar volumes with relative molar masses for the cobalt(III)-nitroammine series of complexes: $(3+)$ $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6]^{3+}$, $(2+)$ $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5(\text{NO}_2)]^{2+}$, $(1+)$ $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_4(\text{NO}_2)_2]^{+}$, (0) $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_3(\text{NO}_2)_3]^{-}$ and $(-)$ $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{NO}_2)_4]^{-}$.

perhaps the strong hydrogen-bonding interactions with the steadily increasing number of nitro-ligands dominates this situation.

The overall pattern of partial molar volumes for cobalt(III) complexes is summarised in Fig. 2, where $\bar{V}$ (complex) is plotted against RMM. We would have preferred to use intrinsic molar volumes for the x-axis in this plot, but such data are only available for a limited number of cobalt(III) complexes. The expected general correlation is apparent, but it is difficult to discern a clear pattern for deviations from the correlation. There is a general tendency for the more hydrophobic species to lie above the mean correlation line, the more hydrophilic below. Both high charge and hydrophilic character of coordinated ligands tend to lower positions on this graph. It is unfortunate that the points cluster in a relatively small area, with extremely few points at high $\bar{V}$ (RMM) values. One of the reasons for our investigation of molar volumes for binuclear cobalt(III) complexes is to obtain data to fill the gap between the vast majority of points in Fig. 2 and the isolated points for $[\text{Co}(\text{phen})_3]^{3+}$ and $[\text{Co}(\text{terpy})_2]^{2+}$ (which have hydrophobic peripheries) and the (fairly hydrophilic) tetranuclear hexol cation.

Transfer chemical potentials : Our new solubility results, for salts of mono- and of binuclear complexes, are reported in Table 5. This Table also

shows the derivations of the transfer chemical potentials $\delta_m \mu^0$ of the respective cobalt(III) complexes. The single ion values are on the TPTB assumption, $\delta_m \mu^0(\text{PPh}_4^-) = \delta_m \mu^0(\text{BPh}_4^-)$, with $\delta_m \mu^0$ values for Cl^- , Br^- , K^+ and SO_4^{2-} counterions taken from published compilations^{26,27}.

The general pattern of transfer chemical potentials for cobalt(III) complexes from water into aqueous methanol, is shown in Fig. 3. These trends are derived from a variety of sources, cited in Table 6^{6,26-28}; the picture in Fig. 3 is considerably fuller than in our previous version of such a plot²¹ thanks to several sets of recently published data. The sequence of complexes in Fig. 3 can readily be rationalised in terms of the charges on the complexes and the hydrophilic/hydrophobic nature of their peripheries.

The position of binuclear complexes in this pattern is shown in Fig. 4; the same factors clearly operate. Thus the trends for $[(\text{H}_2\text{N})_4\text{Co}(\mu\text{-NH}_2)(\mu\text{-OH})\text{Co}(\text{CO}_3)_2]$ and $[(\text{H}_2\text{N})_3(\mu\text{-CO}_3)(\mu\text{-OH})_2\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_3]^{2+}$, a rather similar pair of binuclear species, are close to that for two moles of their mononuclear analogue $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_4(\text{CO}_3)]^+$. The difference between the trends for the former binuclear complex and its dien analogue is similar to that between the trends for $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6]^{3+}$ and $[\text{Co}(\text{en})_3]^{3+}$. These initial results and comparisons are encouraging, but several more transfer chemical

Fig. 2. Correlation of partial molar volumes for cobalt(III) complexes with their relative molecular masses: (hexol = $[\text{Co}\{(\mu\text{-OH})_2\text{Co}(\text{en})_2\}_2]^{4+}$).

Fig. 3 Transfer chemical potential trends for cobalt(III) complexes in methanol-water mixtures.

TABLE 5—SOLUBILITIES OF SALTS OF COBALT(III) COMPLEXES IN METHANOL-WATER MIXTURES AND DERIVATION OF THE TRANSFER CHEMICAL POTENTIALS OF THE RESPECTIVE COMPLEX IONS (298.2 K ; MOLAR SCALE ; TPTB SINGLE ION ASSUMPTION)

Methanol vol %	0	10	20	30	40	50	60
[Co(NH₃)₆]Br₃							
abs	1.75	1.26	0.89	0.63	0.44	0.29	0.17
Δ(salt)		+3.3	+6.7	+10.1	+13.8	+17.8	+22.9
Δ(Br ⁻)		+0.1	+0.3	+0.7	+1.1	+1.9	+2.9
Δ(complex)		+3.0	+5.7	+8.0	+10.4	+12.1	+14.1
[Co(NH₃)₄(CO₃)₂]SO₄							
abs	2.86	1.33	0.57	0.192	0.071	0.020	0.005
Δ(salt)		+5.7	+12.0	+20.1	+27.5	+36.9	+47.2
Δ(SO ₄ ²⁻)		+2.7	+6.0	+9.4	+13.0	+18.0	+23.0
Δ(complex)		+1.5	+3.0	+5.3	+7.2	+9.4	+12.1
[Co(en)₃]Cl₃							
abs	71				32		
Δ(salt)					+8		
Δ(Cl ⁻)					+2		
Δ(complex)					+2		
[Co(en)₃]Br₃							
abs	1.34	1.13	0.98	0.86	0.78	0.67	
Δ(salt)		+1.7	+3.2	+4.5	+5.4	+6.9	
Δ(Br ⁻)		0	0	0	0	+0.4	
Δ(complex)		+1.7	+3.2	+4.5	+5.4	+6.5	
K₃[Co(CN)₆]							
abs	264		129		92		
Δ(salt)			+7.1		+15.7		
Δ(K ⁺)			+2.2		+5.2		
Δ(complex)			+0.5		+3.1		
$\begin{array}{c} \text{NH}_3 \\ \diagdown \quad \diagup \\ (\text{H}_2\text{N})_4\text{Co} \quad \text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_4 \\ \diagup \quad \diagdown \\ \text{OH} \end{array} \text{Cl}_4$							
abs	1.121	0.80	0.53	0.37	0.215	0.083	0.015
Δ(salt)		+4.2	+9.4	+13.8	+20.4	+32.3	+52.5
Δ(Cl ⁻)		+0.4	+0.8	+1.4	+2.0	+4.3	+7.5
Δ(complex)		+2.6	+6.2	+8.2	+12	+15	+23
$\begin{array}{c} \text{CO}_3 \\ \diagdown \quad \diagup \\ (\text{H}_2\text{N})_2\text{Co} \quad \text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2 \\ \diagup \quad \diagdown \\ \text{OH} \end{array} (\text{ClO}_4)_2$							
abs	15.0		4.7		3.2		1.3
Δ(salt)			+8.6		+11.5		+18.5
Δ(ClO ₄ ⁻)			+0.1		-0.1		+0.3
Δ(complex)			+8.4		+11.7		+17.9
$\begin{array}{c} \text{CO}_3 \\ \diagdown \quad \diagup \\ (\text{dien})\text{Co} \quad \text{Co}(\text{dien}) \\ \diagup \quad \diagdown \\ \text{OH} \end{array} (\text{ClO}_4)_2$							
abs	0.120	0.105	0.102	0.079	0.072	0.060	
Δ(salt)		+1.0	+1.2	+3.1	+3.8	+5.2	
Δ(ClO ₄ ⁻)		0	+0.1	0	-0.1	0	
Δ(complex)		+1.0	+1.0	+3.1	+4.0	+5.2	

TABLE 6—SOURCES OF PUBLISHED TRANSFER CHEMICAL POTENTIAL DATA FOR COBALT(III) COMPLEXES

Complex type	Ligand(s)	Ref.
[Co(NH ₃) ₆ L] ⁿ⁺	NH ₃	28
	Cl ⁻	6
	Br ⁻	29
	NCS ⁻	30
[Co(NH ₃) ₄ (LL)] ⁿ⁺	(H ₂ O) ₂ (<i>cis</i>)	31
	CO ₃ ²⁻	31
<i>trans</i> -[CoL ₂ Cl ₂] ⁺	py	32
	4Etpy	33
	phen	34
[Co(phen) ₂ (LL)] ⁿ⁺	CO ₃ ²⁻	31
	Cl ₂ (<i>trans</i>)	35
[Co(en) ₂ L ₂] ⁿ⁺	ox ³⁻	31
	SCH ₃ CO ₂ ⁻	30
[Co(sepulchrate)] ³⁺		27
[Co(μ-OH) ₂ Co(NH ₃) ₄] ²⁺		31

potential trends for binuclear cobalt(III) complexes are needed before detailed discussion is in order. Unfortunately there are problems in further developments along these lines, since it is often difficult to find salts of the appropriately low solubility which is essential when dealing with complex ions of relatively high charges such as the 4+ and 5+ commonly exhibited.

Transfer chemical trends for methanol-water mixtures are put into context of other series of mixed aqueous solvents in Fig. 5 for the [Co(NH₃)₄(CO₃)]²⁺ and [Co(NH₃)₅Br]²⁺ cations. We conclude by mentioning that transfer chemical potentials for the [Co(NH₃)₆]³⁺ and [Co(en)₂(CO₃)]²⁺ cations have

Fig. 4. Transfer chemical potential trends for binuclear cobalt(III) complexes in methanol-water mixtures.

Fig. 5. Transfer chemical potential trends for (a) $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_4(\text{CO}_3)]^+$ and (b) $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6\text{Br}]^{2+}$ in alcohol-water mixtures.

recently been determined for water-ammonia mixtures³⁶; unfortunately no direct comparison can at the moment be made with our results. Such comparison is ruled out not only by the different natures of the substrates but also by the different single ion assumptions used.

Experimental

The complexes $[(H_3N)_4Co(\mu-NH_2)(\mu-OH)Co(NH_3)_4]Cl_4$ ³⁷, $[Co(NH_3)_6]Br_3$ ³⁸, $[Co(NH_3)_4(CO_3)_2]SO_4$ ³⁹, $[Co(en)_3]Cl_3$ ⁴⁰, $[Co(en)_3]Br_3$ ⁴¹, $K_3[Co(CN)_6]$ ⁴², $[(H_3N)_4Co(\mu-NH_2)(\mu-OH)Co(CO_3)_2]$ ⁴³, $[(H_3N)_2Co(\mu-CO_3)(\mu-OH)_2Co(NH_3)_3](ClO_4)_2$ ⁴⁴ and $[(dien)Co(\mu-CO_3)(\mu-OH)_2Co(dien)](ClO_4)_2$ ⁴⁴ were prepared and purified by published methods.

Techniques and methods for the derivation and calculation of results, for partial molar volumes via densities⁴⁵ and for transfer chemical potentials via solubilities²⁷, were as described previously.

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